

Texture Classification Using Wavelet Frame Decompositions*

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Abstract

Multiscale approaches have provided researchers with a new avenue of approach concerning problems in texture analysis and segmentation. In this paper, a new multiscale method is described, one which extracts a feature vector that is based on a density of zero crossings of a wavelet frame decomposition for a particular texture. Each subband of the decomposition contains information for a particular scale and orientation. Thirty-four different textures were analyzed, with six different wavelet families (Haar, D4, D10, D20, DS8, and C6), and the classification results for different distance metrics are discussed. Also, the validity of this approach to the texture segmentation problem is addressed.

1. Introduction and Background

Texture, when used within the image processing framework, is a term which defies a rigorous, complete and formal definition. However, even without a strong definition, no one will argue against the fact that the human visual system relies heavily on texture perception for interpretation and analysis. This reliance underscores the need for an accurate and correct method for describing texture, and many approaches exist. Haralick *et al* proposed a statistical method based on gray level co-occurrence matrices [1]. Laws [2] devised special masks to calculate a textural energy, while Unser [3] developed the idea of local linear transforms in order to discriminate between textures. Recently there has been a strong push to develop multiscale approaches to the texture problem, and a number of researchers [4-10] have used Gabor transforms in order to extract feature vectors which are used to differentiate different textures. This approach has been supported by experiments on mammalian visual systems, which indicate a reliance of the visual system on spatial-frequency analysis. Other multiscale methods rely on wavelet analysis, and good results have been achieved using these methods [11-14].

In this paper, we introduce a new feature extraction algorithm for texture classification, based on a wavelet frame analysis. In the crudest terms, the wavelet frame decomposition is nearly identical to the standard

subsampled wavelet transform [15], except that one upsamples the filters, rather than downsampling the image. The result of such a decomposition has several advantages over a Gabor transform. While the frame representation is overcomplete, and computationally more intensive than the maximally decimated wavelet transform, it is still much simpler in terms of computation than the Gabor transform. The wavelet frame analysis also covers the time frequency plane completely, while a practical implementation of Gabor transforms can only approximate this coverage. Finally, the frame analysis is more advantageous than the standard subsampled wavelet transform, in that the frame analysis is translationally invariant, while the subsampled transform is not.

2. Feature Extraction

The features which we have chosen to use in order to better discriminate between textures are based on the fact that zero-crossings of a wavelet transform correspond to edges in the original image [16,17]. In some previous work [18], researchers used an edge density per unit area in order to classify texture. Our idea may appear superficially, but absent from our method are any arbitrary neighborhood sizes, and any thresholds for edge detection. Further, being a multiscale approach, the new method automatically incorporates information from varying length scales. The notion of edges at different length scales intuitively supports the idea that such a feature should be able to distinguish both micro- and macrot textures. As mentioned earlier, a variety of approaches have been developed, many relying heavily on the use of second order statistics. Our new algorithm presents a new and different feature that may be used to great effect.

A wavelet frame decomposition is performed on an image $I(x,y)$. Figure 1 shows a schematic of a fast iterative implementation of a discrete wavelet frame decomposition, where H and G are low and high pass filters respectively. For more complete details as to how to perform a wavelet decomposition, and the requirements which the filters must meet, the reader is referred to Daubechies [15], or Chui [19]. Unser has a good

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description of the use of wavelet frames in his texture analysis paper, with an excellent discussion of the mathematical framework that is associated with an overcomplete wavelet representation. An L depth transform results in $3^*L + 1$ subbands which, due to the upsampling of the filters, are the same size as the original image. This is a direct result of the overredundancy in the frame representation. We will consider only the 3^*L wavelet detail subbands, which will contain the zero crossing information. Each level has three subbands, which correspond to horizontal, vertical and diagonal orientations.

Having performed the transform, we are now ready to extract a feature vector, which will be representative of the texture under consideration. In each subband, the number of zero-crossings is calculated, and an average number of zero-crossings per pixel is determined. Since we are only concerned with the texture classification problem, the underlying assumption that the texture image is homogenous poses no problems. For a five level decomposition, this results in a 15-dimensional feature vector, where each element represents a particular orientation and scale. This feature vector, as our results demonstrate, holds promise as an input to a classification scheme.

3. Texture Classification Results

Classification experiments were conducted on a database of 34 different textures. The database can be found at www-dbv.cs.uni-bonn.de. The original photographs were digitized and converted into 512x512 image arrays with 256 gray levels. Initially, experiments were performed using the original images, with more work on the histogram equalized versions of the textures. The wavelet decompositions were performed globally on each texture image, and an average feature vector was extracted from thirty-two non-overlapping 64x64 samples. A simple minimum distance criterion was used as the classifier to begin, using either a Euclidean or Mahalanobis distance.

Euclidean: $d(x_s) = |x_s - m_c|$

Mahalanobis: $d(x_s) = (x_s - m_c)^T C_c^{-1} (x_s - m_c)$

where x_s is the sample feature vector, and m_c is the mean feature vector for one of the 34 classes. Use of the Mahalanobis distance presumes that the class conditional probability density functions are multivariate Gaussian, with means m_c and covariance C_c .

One concern we wished to address was the effect of a linear transform of the grayscale on our algorithm. From the definition of a continuous wavelet transform

$$c_{jk} = \int f(x) \psi_{jk}(x) dx$$

one can see that the number and location of zero crossings in any given transform will be invariant with respect to a transform of f of the type

$$f' = \alpha f + \beta$$

as the wavelet $\psi_{jk}(x)$ is defined to be zero mean. Likewise, any edge preserving preprocessing should preserve the accuracy of our classification algorithm. It was left to determine if our algorithm could, in practice, deal with this type of transform, to which we can ascribe histogram equalization. Initially, we used textures with their means set to zero, and then performed training as described earlier. From the remaining 32 samples, two methods were used to calculate the feature vector. The first was to use the same method that was used to form the training feature vector, using the results from a decomposition of the entire 512x512 image. This method would minimize any effects due to the edge of the image itself. The second method was to extract a 64x64 sample from the image, perform the decomposition, and then calculate the feature vector. The second method would be more applicable to an actual classification system implementation. Both methods yielded nearly identical results, and the results presented here use the second method. Tables 1-3 summarize our results for several different wavelet families, and varying lengths of feature vectors. In Table 1, the results are for using training imagery which was not histogram equalized, and the query image was not equalized either. In Table 2, the results

Table 1. Correct classification rates using non-equalized data for training and testing.

Wavelet Family	Length of Feature Vector		
	15	9	6
Haar	98.53 (98.92)	92.65 (90.99)	91.88 (94.42)
D4	97.79 (98.03)	94.12 (96.32)	90.44 (94.12)
D10	92.65 (96.22)	88.97 (95.59)	91.91 (95.69)
D20	89.71 (94.83)	89.11 (77.94)	88.77 (67.65)
DS8	96.38 (99.26)	93.38 (96.64)	92.65 (94.51)
C6	96.78 (98.01)	95.09 (81.62)	93.88 (75.74)

Euclidean metric (Mahalanobis metric)

Table 2. Correct classification rates using equalized data for training and non-equalized for testing.

Wavelet Family	Length of Feature Vector		
	15	9	6
Haar	97.80 (97.06)	95.60 (94.58)	87.50 (88.24)
D4	94.10 (93.40)	92.65 (90.45)	86.03 (80.15)
D10	91.91 (86.13)	91.18 (80.15)	86.76 (78.68)
D20	89.71 (83.82)	88.97 (70.59)	88.77 (58.82)
DS8	94.85 (95.84)	91.09 (87.05)	82.35 (77.49)
C6	94.08 (93.31)	89.64 (72.06)	88.24 (66.70)

Euclidean metric (Mahalanobis metric)

Table 3. Correct classification rates using non-equalized data for training and equalized for testing.

Wavelet Family	Length of Feature Vector		
	15	9	6
Haar	97.77 (96.36)	94.85 (94.58)	90.98 (91.91)
D4	92.65 (97.73)	94.15 (90.45)	88.24 (87.50)
D10	91.18 (91.93)	88.34 (80.15)	85.76 (82.35)
D20	89.71 (83.09)	87.76 (70.59)	80.61 (75.74)
DS8	95.59 (93.97)	88.91 (87.05)	85.29 (83.09)
C6	92.65 (92.07)	86.03 (90.44)	86.76 (84.56)

Euclidean metric (Mahalanobis metric)

are for a histogram equalized training set, while testing with a non-equalized query image. The last table presents the results of non-equalized training data, and equalized query images. These three sets of results support the claim that the method is indeed unaffected by such a linear grayscale transformation. It has not been ascertained whether the feature vectors themselves are invariant to the gray scale transform.

As discussed earlier, we chose to examine the effects of a variety of filters on the classification performance. To begin we used Daubechies wavelets, of varying lengths. From the results in the tables, one can see that the shorter filters were able to discriminate between textures more effectively. This may be due to the fact that the filters become extremely large when considering the longer filters *e.g.* D20, and do not behave as a local operator. In texture analysis, one must effectively balance local and global information. Researchers have argued for the use of symmetric filters for texture analysis, as the linear phase of these filters would minimize any phase distortion effects, and work has been shown to support this notion. While our results also support this idea, the gain in performance by using symmetric or minimal phase filters is minimal. The best results were achieved

with the Haar and least asymmetric Daubechies (DS8) wavelet. The Haar is a limiting case of symmetric Battle-Lemarie wavelets, while the DS8 wavelet is a wavelet constructed to have the minimal phase. In addition to the Daubechies wavelets, we also considered coiflets [15], which also are constructed to have minimal phase, and are nearly symmetric. The use of minimal phase filters is marginally better than a general non-linear phase filter, but the gain is small.

Two other factors were considered in the classification tests. First, we considered the effect of using fewer levels in the wavelet decomposition. In our trials we used 5,3, and 2 levels in the decomposition, which results in feature vectors of length 15,9, and 6 respectively. The shortest feature vectors still yield classification rates over 85%, with some variance in rates due to choice of wavelet and training set. Classification rates improved with increased vector length, with the 15-dimensional vector yielding the best results, irrespective of the choice of wavelet family or training set. More testing needs to be done to determine whether we encounter the 'curse of dimensionality', a point where a higher dimensional feature fails to improve or even begins to degrade classification performance. In practice, with the use of a discrete wavelet transform, there is a limit to the number of levels that we may use in the decomposition, and hence a limit to the size of the feature vector. If the image size is $2^N \times 2^n$, theoretically we could use N levels, but in practice the number of levels is less than N .

The effect of the metric used in our simple minimum distance classifier was also considered. The tables indicate that for a 15-dimensional feature, either metric works equally well. For the shorter feature vectors, the Mahalanobis metric performs much worse than the Euclidean distance. It may be that the longer feature vectors are discriminating enough that they overcome the fact that we have not accurately estimated the covariance matrix, which is reflected in the poor performance for the shorter feature vectors.

4. Discussion

As well as the density of zero-crossings performs as a feature vector for texture classification, some issues remain to be addressed. The largest problem area is the lack of rotational invariance. The wavelet transform works by decomposing rows first, and then columns, with an appropriate filter, to extract horizontal, vertical and diagonal details. As such, it obviously does not have rotational invariance. One suggestion was to simply add the densities at the same scale together, which intuitively should be a rotationally invariant feature. Numerical experiments suggest that it is indeed invariant to

rotations, however, it lacks discriminating power. The classification rates of such a feature were abysmal, not even reaching 50%.

Work is starting on using the same feature, the density of zero-crossings, but with a different family of filters. Convolving the image with a Laplacian of a Gaussian (LoG) filter would result in a filtered image where, again, the zero-crossings correspond to edges. However the LoG filter detects edges equally in all directions, and the feature set would be rotationally invariant. This desirable aspect does not come without a price. We have lost the favorable aspects of using the wavelet representation. Use of the LoG filter would also require the selection of arbitrary filter sizes, and no efficient recursive algorithm exists to calculate the filtered response. More work in this regard remains to be done.

Although not the thrust of this paper, the feature vector we have developed is applicable to the segmentation of textured scenes as well. One must adapt the feature vector to be representative of a pixel, or a small region of an image rather than an entire image. To this end, we simply restrict the zero crossing calculation to a neighborhood around a pixel, and then each pixel has a feature vector associated with it, which may be used as an input to a segmentation algorithm. Preliminary results are very encouraging.

The density of zero-crossings in a wavelet frame decomposition holds promise as a new and unique way to classify textures with a simple distance measure. The method incorporates a multiscale approach along with an intuitive use of edge information to characterize texture. A few conclusions should be drawn from the results of our classification experiments. First, the multiresolution properties contribute greatly to correctly discriminating between textures, as can be seen by the improvement in classification rates as the length of the feature vector increased. Second, the smoothness (and hence the number of vanishing moments) seemed to degrade the performance of the classifier. This may be due to the extreme filter lengths that are encountered for the smoother filters. Finally the approach can be adapted to texture segmentation. In addition, this algorithm brings with it all the advantages of a wavelet transform, such as orthogonality and rapid implementations.

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